

Hemin-Collodion Membrane Electrode for the Measurement of Anion Activity in (Aquo) Electrolytic Solutions : Part III. NO₂⁻, ClO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, and BrO₃⁻ activities

G. K. Pillai and D. R. Pandit

In the thin coherent hemin collodion film membranes prepared by a modified method, Cl⁻ ion in the film could be exchanged by NO₂⁻, ClO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻, and BrO₃⁻ ions by keeping it in contact with neutral aqueous solutions of the respective salts for a prolonged period, the conditioning time varied with the nature of the ions.

The film membranes of different salts of hematin prepared could be used in the determination of anion activities of the neutral aqueous solutions of different electrolytes from the measurement of membrane potential. In the case of KNO₂ the valid range of concentration for the application of Nernst equation was 0.0002 to 0.08 *M* with molarity ratio 2, and the same for KClO₃, KClO₄ and KBrO₃ were (1) 0.0008 to 0.0512 *M*, (2) 0.0002 to 0.0512 *M* and (3) 0.0016 to 0.0512 *M* respectively, the experimental error in the measurement being ±3.5%.

In continuation of our previous work^{1,2}, attempts have been made to ascertain the utilities of film membranes of nitrite, bromate, chlorate and perchlorate of hematin obtained by exchange of Cl⁻ ion in hemin collodion membrane electrode, in the determination of the anion activities of neutral aqueous solutions of various salts, at different molarity ratios from the measurement of membrane potential. The valid range of concentrations for which the Nernst equation could accurately be applied has been determined in each case.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the measurement of anion activities, the electrolytes, KNO₂, KClO₃, KClO₄, KBrO₃ used were of B.D.H., E. Merck, or AnalaR grade. All the stock solutions were 0.1*M*, made by dissolving the appropriate quantity of the salt in Co₂-free distilled water, the other solutions of required strength were prepared by proper dilution.

Hemin collodion film membranes of different thicknesses were prepared by a different modified process than followed previously in our work^{1,2}. Weighed quantity of finely-powdered hemin (B.D.H.) was dispersed in a dilute solution of known concentration of inert collodion in a mixture of ethanol and ether (1 : 4) in a Pyrex glass-stoppered bottle. In the mixture the weight to weight ratio of the Hemin to collodion was kept 30 to 70%. The mixture was shaken mechanically for thorough mixing for 4 hrs. Then it was placed between two flat and uniform stainless steel metallic surfaces and subjected to a pressure of, 1300 lbs p.s.i. under hydraulic press. The blackish brown film membranes thus prepared were soft, coherent and uniform, the thickness of different films varied between 0.12 mm

1. D. R. Pandit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 917.
2. D. R. Pandit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 432.

and 0.83 mm. These film membranes were then soaked in water for 48 hrs to swell and then in 0.5 to 1.0M aqueous electrolytic solutions of KNO_2 , KClO_3 and KBrO_3 for time ranging from 48 hrs to several days, depending upon the anion of the electrolyte to be exchanged with chloride ion in the hemin-collodion film. In the case of KClO_4 , 0.115M aqueous solution was used for soaking the film membrane. It was observed that for conditioning the film membranes with KClO_4 and KBrO_3 prolonged soaking of about 40 days were required before they could develop a stable membrane potential. But once these film membranes were conditioned properly with the required critical anion the performance were very satisfactory as could be seen from the tabulated results. The prolonged conditioning period observed in the case of Hemin collodion film membranes was also observed by Basu³ in the case of pyrocatechol formaldehyde resin membrane and *p*-phenol sulfonic acid resin membranes. Possible reason for the long conditioning time may be that during the preparation of the film membranes under pressure, Hemin particles become so oriented that the exchange sites instead of being exposed to the surface of the film membrane, remain deeply buried inside the membrane. This required long contact period with the electrolytes containing the critical ions. The experimental methods were the same as followed in our previous work^{1,2}. For using the film as membrane electrode, uniform film membrane properly conditioned with the required critical ion was fitted between two rubber washers to the end of a glass tube (1.5 cm. dia) on which an insulated metal cap could be screwed up.

The e.m.f. of the cell was determined by placing electrolytic solutions of different ionic concentrations inside and outside the tube i.e., on two sides of the membrane and dipping two small saturated calomel electrodes of the same electrode potential in the ambient solutions. After introducing the electrodes and adjusting the liquids inside and outside the tube to the same level to prevent hydrostatic pressure on the membrane, the e.m.f. readings were made with the help of Bajaj potentiometer reading between the ranges (1) 0.01 to 20 mv. and (2) 0.05 to 105 mv. using a ballistic mirror galvanometer as the null point instrument. Only those portion of the film membranes, which showed zero or negligible asymmetry potential in case of solutions of same concn. on two sides, were used in anion activity determination. All experiments were made at 25°.

For calculating the activities of NO_2^- , ClO_3^- , BrO_3^- and ClO_4^- ions in solutions of various concn. the activity coefficients of these ions were obtained by graphically plotting the values recorded by Conway⁴. For comparison, the theoretical e.m.f. was calculated from the Nernst equation

$$\bar{E} = \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

The experimental and the theoretical values of membrane potential with electrolytic solutions of KNO_2 , KClO_3 , KBrO_3 and KClO_4 using films of thickness varying from 0.12 mm to 0.81 mm at different molarity ratios are recorded in the Table I.

3. A. S. Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 616.

4. B. C. Conway, "Electro-chemical Data", Elsevier Publication, N.Y., 1952, p. 102.

TABLE I

Membrane potentials of Hemin-Collodion Membranes
Temperature of Measurement—25°

1. Electrolyte 2. Film Thickness 3. Molarity Ratio	Molarity $\times 10^{-3}$		Anion activity $\times 10^{-3}$		Membrane potential (m.v.)	
	Inside	Outside	Inside	Outside	Cal.	Obs.
1. KNO_2 2. 0.12 m.m. 3. 2 : 1	00.40	00.20	00.394	00.197	17.70	17.00
	00.78	00.39	00.762	00.383	17.68	17.55
	01.56	00.78	01.515	00.762	17.64	17.50
	03.12	01.56	02.986	01.515	17.43	17.35
	06.25	03.12	05.863	02.986	17.34	17.30
	12.50	06.25	11.480	05.863	17.27	17.20
	25.00	12.50	22.20	11.48	16.94	17.15
	50.00	25.00	42.50	22.20	16.68	17.65
1. KNO_2 2. 0.12 m.m. 3. 3 : 1	60.00	30.00	50.28	26.31	16.63	16.60
	80.00	40.00	64.96	34.48	16.27	16.00
	00.30	00.10	00.295	00.099	28.07	26.00
	00.90	00.30	00.878	00.295	28.02	27.00
	02.70	00.90	02.587	00.878	27.75	27.70
	08.10	02.70	07.533	02.587	27.46	27.40
	24.30	08.10	21.55	07.533	27.01	26.95
	72.90	24.30	60.65	21.55	26.59	26.50
1. KClO_3 2. 0.12 m.m. 3. 2 : 1	80.00	26.70	64.96	23.55	26.07	25.35
	01.60	00.80	01.549	00.782	17.55	18.25
	03.20	01.60	03.059	01.549	17.48	17.55
	06.40	03.20	06.009	03.059	17.35	17.30
	12.80	06.40	11.74	06.009	17.21	17.10
	25.60	12.80	22.71	11.74	16.95	16.75
	51.20	25.60	43.72	22.71	16.83	15.95
	03.20	01.60	03.059	01.549	17.48	18.10
1. KBrO_3 2. 0.81 m.m. 3. 2 : 1	06.40	03.20	06.009	03.059	17.35	17.80
	12.80	06.40	11.74	06.009	17.21	17.50
	25.60	12.80	22.71	11.74	16.95	17.00
	51.20	25.60	43.72	22.71	16.85	16.00
	00.40	00.20	00.393	00.197	17.73	17.50
	00.80	00.40	00.782	00.393	17.70	17.85
	01.60	00.80	01.549	00.782	17.55	17.65
	03.20	01.60	03.059	01.549	17.48	17.50
1. KClO_4 2. 0.17 m.m. 3. 2 : 1	06.40	03.20	06.009	03.059	17.35	17.40
	12.80	06.40	11.74	06.009	17.21	17.10
	25.60	12.80	22.71	11.74	16.95	16.50
	51.20	25.60	43.72	22.71	16.83	16.25

DISCUSSION

Hemin prepared from hemoglobin according to the method suggested by Lewis⁵ and Kuester⁶ has the formula $C_{34}H_{32}O_4N_4FeCl$. According to Lindonfield⁷, Kuhu and Furter⁸ hemin contains electrovalently bound Cl^- ion and replaceable H atoms covalently bound in $-COOH$ groups, but it does not behave as a polyampholyte as there is no influence of pH on the membrane potential in the film membranes of hemin in the pH range of 0.0 to 7.4 as described in Part I¹. Lindonfield⁷ could replace electrovalently bound Cl^- ion of hemin with Br^- , I^- or other acid radicals and he observed that the law of mass action was followed in this ion exchange. Hemin is thus an anion exchanger. The Cl^- ion in hemin-collodion film membrane could be completely exchanged with NO_3^- , I^- and IO_3^- ions as confirmed by the constancy of membrane potential in the concn. range of 0.0015 to 0.05 M as discussed in Part II². In the present work more coherent and uniform Hemin-collodion films were used. The membrane potential recorded in the e.m.f. observed column are the mean of the two sets of measurement made by reversing the concn. inside and outside the film membrane. From the results recorded in Table I, it can be seen that in the case of NO_2^- ions there is fairly a good agreement (within experimental error of $\pm 3.5\%$) between the observed and the theoretical values, calculated from Nernst equation at 25°; with molarity ratio 2 the valid range of concentration is from 0.0002 to 0.08 M in neutral aqueous solutions of KNO_2 , while for the same ion the valid range is from 0.0001 to 0.080 M with molarity ratio 3. In the case of ClO_3^- and ClO_4^- ions the range of validity is from 0.0008 to 0.0512 M and from 0.0002 to 0.0512 M respectively with molarity ratio 2; whereas for BrO_3^- ions the valid range of concentration is from 0.0016 to 0.0512 M , the error in membrane potential ranging from 0.4 to 3.5%. In the case of the neutral electrolytic solution of $KClO_3$, $KBrO_3$ and $KClO_4$, at concentrations higher than 0.0512 M the e.m.f. values obtained were lower than the theoretical values; due to comparatively lower concn. of the critical ion in the membrane at this stage and consequent decrease in T.No. of the critical ion, which is unity at lower concn. of the outside solution; similar lowering was also observed by Sollner⁹ in the case of protaminecollodion membrane and by Basu¹⁰ in his studies of resin membrane electrodes.

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Department of Chemistry,
N. M. Institute of Science,
Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan's College,
Andheri, Bombay-58.

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5. Lewis, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1954, **206**, 109.
6. Kuester, *Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1913, **82**, 463.
7. K. Lindonfield, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1935, **15**, 516.
8. Kuhu and Furter, *Ber.*, 1928, **61B**, 127.
9. K. Sollner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 409.
10. A. S. Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 622.